

Benchmark datasets for predictive maintenance challenges in steel manufacturing

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a set of six benchmark datasets for predictive maintenance in Industry 4.0. We focus on the cold rolling mills in steel production, and use mathematical simulation of the rolling process to generate the data. The datasets vary in complexity, differing in the number of products, types of anomalies, and presence of data shifts. The primary goal of these datasets is to facilitate the development and benchmarking of predictive maintenance methods, particularly those using machine learning techniques. They can be used for development of diagnostic tasks, such as anomaly detection, fault detection or fault diagnosis. Our main motivation stems from the fact that most of the research on predictive maintenance in the steel industry relies on real data from manufacturing sites. Such data is often unlabeled, and not publicly available, making it difficult to reproduce results and compare them with other studies. Our datasets can be used to validate general-purpose methods and serve as an alternative to publicly available datasets from other domains. In this paper, we describe the methodology used to create the datasets, details the anomalies introduced, and provide examples of their use.

Background & Summary

Predictive Maintenance (PdM) is a strategy for keeping the good condition of industrial machinery, which utilizes the advanced data analytics to predict equipment malfunctions as soon as possible. The objectives of PdM include minimizing downtime, reducing operational costs, and ensuring high product quality. These methods can be widely adopted across various industries, including steel production, which is a crucial industry that supplies materials for sectors such as construction, automotive, energy, and manufacturing. One of the integral steps of steel production process is cold rolling, which aims to reduce the thickness of hot-rolled steel. Like in any other industrial process, presence of anomalies or failures during cold rolling, may lead to unexpected downtime, quality losses or reduced performance.

One of the most important fields related to the development of PdM methods is Machine Learning (ML), which can be widely applied to address different PdM tasks such as anomaly detection, fault prediction or remaining useful life estimation. ML provides tools and techniques to analyze large volumes of data from industrial processes, enabling the identification of patterns related with normal working conditions and degradation. The development of ML methods in industrial settings, including tandem cold mills (TCM), is often hampered by a lack of high-quality datasets. Most research on predictive maintenance in the steel industry depends on proprietary, on-site data that tends to be unlabeled, and unavailable to the wider community, hindering reproducibility and cross-study comparison[?]. This issue is evident in the development of ML-based PdM methods for cold rolling processes^{?,?,?}. Furthermore, the absence of publicly available industrial data from TCM makes it impossible to benchmark different methods against each other, hindering the clear advancement of PdM methods development. To address these issues, we have developed synthetic datasets from the cold rolling process aimed at identifying anomalies with a physical basis. These datasets can be used to support the development and evaluation of various diagnostic tasks, including anomaly detection, fault detection, and fault diagnosis.

Figure ?? presents a schematic overview of a TCM consisting of five rolling stands. The production process begins with uncoiling the material and feeding it into the mill. As the material gradually moves through the rolling stands, it is gripped, and tensions are established to ensure the stability of the strip. At the mill's exit, the strip is recoiled. Once the recoiler grips the strip, the process accelerates to the target speed and concludes when the entire coil has been rolled and dispatched from the production line.

The synthetic datasets were generated using mathematical model of cold rolling process, available in the literature of the domain, which contains methods for calculation of several key process parameters, i.e., rolling force, torque, speed, tension, gap, thickness reduction, and motor power. In conceptualization of this dataset, research into the existing models of cold rolling

has been undertaken, to provide a reliable simulation of the process. Based on the predefined product parameters and evolving mill parameters, process variables are calculated. To introduce realistic variability, random noise is introduced at several stages of the simulation. The PdM aspect of the datasets is realized through introduction of anomalies, which are related to a specific kind of failures in the process. In total, we generated six diverse datasets, each varying in complexity, to enable benchmarking of methods across various levels of complexity. Easier datasets are characterized by lower number of anomaly types and smaller number of product types. In more complex datasets, we introduce data shifts, requiring the development of methods, which adapt to changes in the process. Simpler datasets can serve as a starting point for developing new methods, while the more challenging ones typically require advanced techniques such as concept drift detection and data stream learning.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of 5-stand tandem cold mill.

Our primary intention is to make these datasets available to the scientific community for benchmarking ML-based PdM methods addressed to cold rolling process. However, these datasets can also be used for the development of general-purpose PdM methods and anomaly detection methods, standing as an alternative to popular synthetic datasets, i.e., simulation of turbofan engine (CMAPSS)² or Tennessee Eastman process (TEP)². While CMAPSS is primarily used for Remaining Useful Life (RUL) prediction, the TEP dataset is more appropriate for anomaly detection and fault diagnosis. Our dataset has more in common with the TEP dataset and can serve similar purposes. However, our simulation is describing completely different manufacturing process, based on the physical equations, whereas TEP is mostly using chemical equations. In the TEP dataset normal and faulty observations are completely separated and each type of fault is simulated sequentially, which is not reflecting real operating conditions of manufacturing plants. In our datasets, the anomalies are injected throughout whole dataset, making it more realistic and suitable for developing online learning models, that learn from streaming data. The additional challenge is related to the occurrence of data shifts² in the two of the introduced datasets. These features increase broadens the possibilities of using it, not only for PdM tasks but also to enhance recent research on domain adaptation and data shift handling in dynamic environments^{2,2}.

In summary, these datasets can advance development of PdM methodologies devoted to industrial processes in general, but with a focus on the cold rolling process. The synthetic nature of this dataset ensures the existence of ground-truth labels for all observations. This allows for the unbiased comparison of different methods, without need of using poorly labeled data from a real manufacturing process. The generation of six different subsets, varying in complexity, enables researchers to verify both simple and complex approaches.

Methods

The mathematical modelling of cold rolling process is well-studied field^{2,2,2,2}. Models of cold rolling were developed to understand the relationships between the process variables and optimize the rolling process to achieve optimal productivity of actual production sites². They typically involve complex equations describing material flow, stress-strain relationships, frictional forces, and deformations. In this work, we have developed such a model, with the aim of simulating the normal and abnormal process behaviors, rather than optimizing the efficiency of actual manufacturing line.

In following subsections, we present the data and methodology used for simulating the process in a TCM. The data needed to simulate the process can be divided into three main groups: (1) product data, (2) mill data, and (3) process variables. The characteristics of the steel product and the parameters of the installation serve as an input to the mathematical model, while the

process variables are the output of the model. They all constitute an integral part of the feature space in our datasets.

Product information

The product data includes the dimensions of the materials (entry thickness, exit thickness, width) and their mechanical properties, which are expressed as stress-strain curves. During cold rolling material undergoes plastic deformation at each rolling stand, resulting in the gradual increase in mechanical properties, such as yield strength. The evolution of yield strength during rolling can be expressed as a function of strain and approximated by the following equation²:

$$\sigma = K\varepsilon^n \tag{1}$$

where σ is yield strength, K is the modulus of plasticity and n the hardening exponent. These are material properties, which can be assumed to be constant for a specific material grade. The total true strain ε of the material is calculated using equation:

$$\varepsilon = \ln \frac{h_{in}}{h_{out}} \tag{2}$$

where h_{in} is the input thickness and h_{out} is the output thickness.

Based on these equations, we generate curves, which model the relationship between the degree of deformation and yield strength of the material. Figure ?? presents six exemplary curves, which specify the steel grade of the product. The deformation of the material is characterized by the total reduction, which is determined as the ratio of thickness change to the initial thickness of the product.

Figure 2. Exemplary relationships between thickness reduction and yield strength of the material.

Mill characteristics

The configuration of the mill plays a crucial role in modeling the cold rolling process. Factors such as the arrangement of rolls, their size, and the power of the machinery determine the equipment setup, including production speed and load distribution. The main parameters that characterize a TCM include:

- Number of the rolling stands – higher number of stands allows for greater total reduction and smaller load at individual stands.
- Characteristics of the motors – they decide the maximum power and speed, which can be achieved during production process, thus influencing production capacity.
- Lubrication parameters – they affect the friction in a rolling gaps and cooling process, impacting both roll wear and the quality of the product.
- Process limits – they determine minimum and maximum values of process variables.

In this work, we have simulated a TCM consisting of five stands, for which we defined the parameters listed above. These parameters are constant throughout the simulation process, except for the cases of imposed data shifts, which are present in two of the datasets.

Figure 3. The overview of the mathematical simulation, which we used to generate datasets from cold rolling process.

Mathematical modelling of rolling process

Given the product information and mill configuration, the observed variables in the rolling mill are determined using mathematical equations that describe the cold rolling process. A high-level overview of the simulation process is presented in Figure ??, which summarizes the main calculation steps that lead to the generation of a single observation in the dataset. The features colored in green are observed (included in the dataset), while those colored in gray are only intermediate features, which are not recorded.

In our mathematical model the first step is to determine the inter-stand tensions. From practical point of view, they are necessary to maintain strip stability, and prevent breakages. Their values are usually determined by engineers based on their expertise and characteristics of products in specific rolling mill. For the sake of simulation, we have defined the tension as the function of yield stress and cross-sectional area of the steel strip.

The thickness reduction achieved at each stand is one of the most critical variables determining the outcomes of the simulation. This reduction affects the necessary load and energy required to achieve the desired deformation. Optimizing reduction is crucial, as it can lead to suboptimal mill setups². Several approaches can be used to determine the reduction schedule, such as harmonic, geometric, or linear methods³. We calculate the reduction schedule similarly to the harmonic approach. This is done by calculating the initial change in thickness at each stand using the formula:

$$\Delta h_i = (h_{in} - h_{out}) \frac{2c_a}{i} \quad (3)$$

where h_i represents the strip thickness after passing through stand i , h_{in} and h_{out} denote the input and output product thicknesses respectively, and c_a stands for the adjustment coefficient. The thickness after each stand is determined based on the calculated change in thickness. Typically, the resultant output thickness differs from the desired thickness. Therefore, the values obtained are adjusted using the following equation:

$$h_{fi} = h_i \frac{h_{out}}{h_5} \quad (4)$$

where h_{fi} represents the final thickness after each stand, h_i denotes the thickness calculated in the preceding step, and h_5 signifies the thickness at the last stand calculated in the preceding step. The thickness of the product before and after each stand, determine the required reduction.

Once the reduction schedule is determined, the key variables that must be calculated in simulation of the rolling process are rolling forces and torques. Accurately estimating these values requires consideration of plasticity theory and rolling mechanics. Some well-known analytical models that meet these criteria include those by Orowan², Bland and Ford² and Alexander². In our simulation, we utilized the model developed by Bland and Ford. A critical variable for an accurate calculation of the roll force and torque is the friction coefficient within the roll gap, specifically between the work rolls and the rolled material. In practice, precisely determining friction in a rolling process is overly complex. However, numerous studies have been conducted to examine the impact of a range of factors on friction. Many of them are summarized in the work by Lenard². We build on this work and simulate friction coefficient as a function of roll speed, work roll mileage, lubrication mileage and reduction. For each stand a friction coefficient is set at slightly different level to better represent variety of real-world conditions. The resulting friction is the average of friction coefficients determined from these four factors. The relationships between the variables and friction coefficient used in our simulation is presented in the Figure ??.

Figure 4. Simulated influence of different rolling variables on the friction coefficient in a roll gap.

Before running the analytical model that calculates forces and torques, an initial speed distribution is determined, based on the predefined stand limits and reduction schedule, so that friction coefficient can be estimated. Except for that, analytical model considers the entry and exit thickness, strip width, tensions, yield strength of the material, and diameter of work rolls. For a detailed description of the calculation procedure, we refer to original paper².

Once the rolling force and torque are determined, we can calculate mechanical power necessary to perform rolling of the material, based on the rolling speed, work roll diameters and torque. It is calculated using simple dynamics²:

$$P_{mi} = M_{ri} \frac{v_i}{0.5D_i} \quad (5)$$

where P_{mi} is the mechanical power of stand i , M_{ri} is the required rolling torque, v_i is the rolling speed and D_i is the diameter of work rolls. In case of exceeding any of the power limits defined in mill configuration, the rolling speed must be decreased, friction recalculated, and analytical model run once again.

The next step is to determine the size of the rolling gap. This is achieved using mill stretch formula², which is a function of material thickness in the stand and rolling force.

$$s_i = h_i - \frac{F_{ri}}{S_i} \quad (6)$$

where s_i is the roll gap, h_i is the exit thickness, F_{ri} is the rolling force and S_i is the mill stiffness, which is defined in mill configuration.

Finally, we calculate the electric power consumption, which is determined by dividing mechanical power by the electric efficiency. This ends the single run of the model and produces one observation in a dataset. The observation contains the measurable variables from a simulation. This includes product variables, mill variables (diameter and mileage of work rolls), and process variables (reduction, tension, speed, force, torque, gap, power). Variables related to mill and process are recorded at each stand, and the total number of features in each of the datasets is 51. Additionally, each record has 16 anomaly labels associated with it, which determine occurrence of anomalies. These are binary labels, in which **TRUE** indicates the occurrence of a given anomaly type.

After each iteration, mill parameters such as work roll mileage, lubricant condition are updated. If the work rolls mileage or lubricant condition exceeds predefined limits, indicating their wear, they are 'replaced', what slightly affects the normal working conditions. The simulation runs in a loop, randomly selecting the next product and its number of repetitions, until the desired size of dataset is obtained. It is important to note that at several points in the calculation process, we introduce Gaussian noise to increase the variability of the simulation, making it more representative to real-world scenarios.

Anomalies

The primary goal of the datasets is to identify anomalies within the simulated process. We introduced four distinct types of anomalies, which impact the simulation at specific stages of the calculation procedure. These anomalies are not necessarily related to common problems that occur in rolling mills. Instead, they are designed in a manner that makes understanding their sources straightforward. Below we provide a list of the introduced anomalies with their descriptions.

1. **Reduction Anomaly** – it is introduced by modifying the adjustment coefficient c_a during reduction schedule calculation. This effects in abnormal reduction scheme. The final thickness of the product remains the same.
2. **Work Roll Anomaly** – it is defined as increased work roll friction. In practice such phenomenon can happen due to invalid preparation of work rolls or poor lubrication.
3. **Bearings Anomaly** – it is defined as increased rolling torque, which is higher than the one calculated from analytical model. Increased torque can be the effect of high mechanical losses due to e.g., problems with bearings.
4. **Electric Anomaly** – it is related to the decreased electrical efficiency, which effects in increased electrical power of the motor, and indicates problems with the specific motor.

Apart from the anomaly related to reduction, the other anomalies are specific to individual stands, resulting in 16 anomaly labels in total. At every iteration there is a small probability of an anomaly occurring in the process. The variables affected depends strictly on the anomaly type and the physical model. In case of anomalies, all parameters at a given stand, which are determined after its occurrence (see Figure ??) will be affected., This means that in case of *Electric Anomaly* only *electric power* are affected, while in case of *Reduction Anomaly* almost all process variables are modified.

Data Shifts

In a real-world industrial problems, we often deal with the issue of changing normal process conditions. These changes, which are referred to as data shift present a challenge in the development of PdM methods. These shifts in data distribution can occur due to a range of factors such as machinery wear, changes in raw materials, or modifications to manufacturing processes. To enforce development of robust algorithms and methods, which can address this issue, we introduced two types of data shift in our simulation.

Firstly, we simulate the introduction of new, previously unseen products that are rolled in TCM. A poor anomaly detection method will inevitably classify all new products as anomalies since such observations were absent from the dataset before. Conversely, a robust method will effectively generalize to predict the normal behavior of the process under new conditions or will learn this behavior as new products emerge.

Secondly, we introduce a shift related to increased production capacity, characterized by heightened power and motor speed. In such a scenario, the new process speed and power consumption will deviate from previous normal working conditions. This necessitates adapting the prediction model to accommodate these new conditions while ideally retaining as much knowledge from the process as possible.

Data Records

The datasets are publicly available in a Zenodo repository². The repository contains six separate files with data, which are saved in comma-separated values (CSV) format. Each file is a separate simulation of a rolling process. The datasets differ by the total number of product types, number of anomaly types and occurrence of data shifts. Each record represents the simulated

conditions of processing a single steel coil. The coil is characterized by product data, i.e., entry thickness, exit thickness, width, entry yield strength and exit yield strength. Each product type can be assigned to multiple coils (records). Table ?? summarizes the datasets.

Dataset	Observations	Anomalies	Share of Anomalies	Features	Anomaly Types	Unique Products	Data Shift
tcm5_dataset_1	20009	1045	5.2%	51	1	4	FALSE
tcm5_dataset_2	20001	1035	5.2%	51	1	20	FALSE
tcm5_dataset_3	20003	981	4.9%	51	4 (16)	4	FALSE
tcm5_dataset_4	20001	925	4.6%	51	4 (16)	20	FALSE
tcm5_dataset_5	20005	1031	5.2%	51	4 (16)	5	TRUE
tcm5_dataset_6	20008	954	4.8%	51	4 (16)	25	TRUE

Table 1. Summary of datasets

The datasets are arranged in increasing order of complexity. The first dataset ([tcm5_dataset_1](#)) comprises only 4 products, 1 anomaly type, and lacks data shifts. Conversely, the last dataset ([tcm5_dataset_6](#)) consists of 25 products, 4 anomaly types (16 if counting the same type of anomaly on different stands separately) and includes data shifts. Table ?? summarizes the features present in the dataset and provides their brief description. The "Suffix" column indicates that certain feature is recorded per each stand, meaning five repetitions of the same physical property. The only exception is the "Tension" feature, which occurs six times.

Feature	Suffixes	Unit	Description
line no.	-	-	no. observation
thickness_entry	-	mm	product entry thickness
thickness_exit	-	mm	product exit thickness
width	-	mm	product width
ys_entry	-	MPa	product entry yield strength
ys_exit	-	MPa	product exit yield strength
work_roll_diam	1 to 5	mm	work roll diameter (stands 1 to 5)
work_roll_mileage	1 to 5	km	work roll mileage (stands 1 to 5)
reduction	1 to 5	-	thickness reduction (stands 1 to 5)
tension	0 to 5	N	tension (0 - before stand 1, 1 to 5 - after stand 1-5)
roll_speed	1 to 5	-	linear work roll speed (stands 1 to 5)
force	1 to 5	N	rolling force (stands 1 to 5)
torque	1 to 5	Nm	rolling torque (stands 1 to 5)
gap	1 to 5	mm	stand gap (stands 1 to 5)
motor_power	1 to 5	kW	electric motor power (stands 1 to 5)
Anomaly_Reduction	-	-	(label) anomaly in reduction scheme
Anomaly_Electric	1 to 5	-	(label) anomaly in electric motor (stands 1 to 5)
Anomaly_Bearing	1 to 5	-	(label) anomaly in stand bearing (stands 1 to 5)
Anomaly_WorkRoll	1 to 5	-	(label) anomaly in work roll friction (stands 1 to 5)

Table 2. Description of Features

Labels indicating occurrence of anomalies are included in the same file as the features used for predicting anomalies. These labels are situated at the end of the tables, with their names beginning with 'Anomaly'. They should not be utilized for training PdM methods, but solely for testing and validation purposes. The records in the datasets follow chronological order, which is expressed in increasing mileage of work rolls and their replacement. Therefore, the records should be treated as a data stream and not shuffled. All types of anomalies, except for reduction (which is point anomaly) last for several observations, which we present in the Figure ??.

Technical Validation

During each simulation of the rolling process, we generated over 20 000 records, with 51 features and 16 corresponding anomaly labels. Within the cold rolling process, numerous strong correlations can be observed among these features. These can be deduced from the background knowledge of the process and the generated data. For example, rolling speeds at each

(a) Work Roll 3 Anomalies(tcm5_dataset_5)

(b) Reduction Anomalies (tcm5_dataset_5)

Figure 5. Examples of anomalies appearing in the datasets. Observations are colored by entry thickness to help distinguish between various products.

stand are highly correlated, as increasing speed at one stand requires increasing speeds on other stands too. Another example is that the force exerted on the material affects the resistance encountered by the rollers, which influences the torque needed to maintain the rolling operation. Figure ?? presents a heatmap of correlations of all features in dataset `tcm_dataset_2`.

Figure 6. Heatmap presenting correlations between the features in the dataset `tcm5_dataset_2`.

Due to the fact that dataset originates from the simulation of a physical process, we possess ground-truth labels, which differentiate normal and abnormal observations. Moreover, the exact source of anomaly is known, as we defined four specific types of anomalies. This allows to easily retrieve the anomalous observations and the corresponding features, which should indicate abnormal state. We designed the simulation to ensure that anomalies can be detected, but ideally, they should not fall outside the boundaries of the normal process. Figure ?? summarizes the distribution of individual features in four out of six datasets. The boxplots present the distribution of data between minimum and maximum bounds, which were determined based on the data from normal (not anomalous) observations. Majority of the data points lie within the range of normal working conditions, with some anomalous observations being outside these bounds.

(a) Dataset: tcm5_dataset_1

(b) Dataset: tcm5_dataset_2

(c) Dataset: tcm5_dataset_4

(d) Dataset: tcm5_dataset_6

Figure 7. Boxplots summarizing the distribution of individual features in all datasets. Minimum and maximum boundaries are determined based on values observed in normal samples.

During the configuration of the simulation parameters, we aimed to ensure that our simulated results were balanced and reasonable in relation to the obtained values of the process variables. Figure ?? shows the distribution of process variables for all stands. The probabilities were estimated using the Kernel Density Estimation method to create more readable plots. We selected the `tcm5_dataset_3` dataset as an example, but the results for other datasets are comparable. We observe that the distributions of process variables align with the typical behavior of the rolling mills. For example, with each stand, the rolling speed increases while the reduction decreases. We do not observe a single bottleneck in terms of motor load, indicating that the simulation parameters are well-balanced.

Figure 8. The distribution of process variables for all stands.

The difficulty of predicting a certain anomaly depends on the type of anomaly and the number of products in the dataset. For example, anomalies related to changes in the reduction schedule affect many features, while anomalies related to electric motor failure influence only one variable. Additionally, a smaller number of products typically makes it easier for ML algorithms to identify the space of normal working conditions. To support these points, Figure ?? shows the distributions of selected features, distinguishing between normal and abnormal samples. We chose datasets `tcm5_dataset_1` and `tcm5_dataset_4` as representative examples. The first dataset reveals a clear shift in several feature distributions, while in the second dataset, such a shift is much less visible.

Figure 9. Histograms presenting differences in feature distribution of normal and anomalous samples for two representative datasets.

Discovering anomalies is relatively easy when we have prior knowledge about the types of anomalies present in the dataset

and their sources. This allows us to focus on a limited number of features to determine if a specific type of anomaly exists in a given observation. This issue is illustrated in Figure ??, which shows the dependencies between the key features related to a specific type of anomaly. As representative examples, we selected `tcm5_dataset_1` and `tcm5_dataset_4`. However, machine learning algorithms lack this prior knowledge and must independently uncover these relationships.

Finally, we validate if the data shifts, which were introduced in the datasets `tcm5_dataset_5` and `tcm5_dataset_6`, can be easily recognized based on the knowledge of their characteristics. Figure ?? presents that in dataset `tcm5_dataset_5` number of products increase after 8000th observation and that average rolling speed and motor power increased after 16000th observation. This is consistent with the actual shifts that we introduced in this dataset. Similar behavior is observed in the dataset `tcm5_dataset_6`.

Table ?? presents the performance of several machine learning models trained for the anomaly detection task. The results show that while anomalies are generally detectable by these models, their performance is far from perfect—particularly on the more challenging datasets. The best results are typically achieved by the Autoencoder model, especially on datasets without data shifts. Half-space Trees, which is an online learning model and updates continuously with each new observation, performed slightly better than batch learning models on datasets 5 and 6 in terms of F1-score. However, the overall performance of online learning models remains modest. These findings suggest that achieving high predictive accuracy on the datasets requires more sophisticated approaches than standard, off-the-shelf methods.

No.		Baseline	AE	PCA	IForest	LODA	OCSVM	HBOS	K-means ^o	HST ^o	OCSVM ^o
1	F1	0.07	0.82	0.29	0.69	0.25	0.56	0.66	0.12	0.35	0.10
	AUCPR	0.06	0.87	0.24	0.79	0.24	0.57	0.75	0.09	0.32	0.06
	AUCROC	0.48	0.97	0.71	0.98	0.79	0.93	0.97	0.54	0.82	0.53
	G-mean	0.40	0.88	0.59	0.80	0.49	0.74	0.78	0.42	0.60	0.45
2	F1	0.06	0.61	0.10	0.32	0.13	0.29	0.16	0.09	0.10	0.06
	AUCPR	0.04	0.64	0.08	0.33	0.11	0.26	0.15	0.05	0.12	0.04
	AUCROC	0.48	0.93	0.61	0.82	0.73	0.82	0.72	0.53	0.64	0.49
	G-mean	0.38	0.74	0.52	0.53	0.37	0.56	0.39	0.46	0.24	0.40
3	F1	0.07	0.77	0.33	0.30	0.47	0.42	0.34	0.13	0.24	0.12
	AUCPR	0.05	0.87	0.32	0.35	0.51	0.45	0.41	0.08	0.20	0.06
	AUCROC	0.46	0.97	0.80	0.85	0.92	0.89	0.87	0.58	0.73	0.53
	G-mean	0.35	0.90	0.70	0.55	0.64	0.74	0.52	0.53	0.61	0.39
4	F1	0.08	0.64	0.08	0.13	0.15	0.22	0.10	0.07	0.16	0.08
	AUCPR	0.05	0.68	0.08	0.11	0.09	0.20	0.08	0.06	0.12	0.04
	AUCROC	0.50	0.93	0.64	0.70	0.67	0.82	0.65	0.54	0.63	0.47
	G-mean	0.46	0.77	0.26	0.59	0.41	0.70	0.53	0.31	0.45	0.43
5	F1	0.07	0.20	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.22	0.09
	AUCPR	0.05	0.60	0.13	0.15	0.05	0.09	0.06	0.06	0.25	0.04
	AUCROC	0.49	0.89	0.62	0.63	0.56	0.58	0.51	0.52	0.63	0.48
	G-mean	0.44	0.73	0.52	0.58	0.51	0.53	0.47	0.45	0.58	0.21
6	F1	0.07	0.13	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.08	0.14	0.08
	AUCPR	0.04	0.34	0.11	0.11	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.04	0.11	0.04
	AUCROC	0.51	0.80	0.61	0.58	0.56	0.62	0.55	0.52	0.66	0.45
	G-mean	0.41	0.67	0.56	0.54	0.52	0.53	0.47	0.35	0.50	0.32

^o Online learning models

Table 3. Performance of several ML models on anomaly detection task. The best result for each metric is shown in bold.

Code availability

The code used for visualization, technical validation and benchmarking of the data and results is openly available. Researchers and interested parties can access the code on our GitHub repository: <https://github.com/jjakubow/pdm-steel-datasets>.

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(a) Dataset: tcm5_dataset_3

(b) Dataset: tcm5_dataset_4

Figure 10. Scatter plots presenting the distribution of the key features related to selected anomalies. The colors of points depict the exit thickness of a material, allowing to differentiate between different types of products.

Figure 11. Timeline of selected features, which present existence of data shift in the dataset `tcm5_dataset_5`.

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Author contributions statement

All authors conceived the experiment, J.J. conducted the experiments, J.J. and S.B. analyzed the results, G.J.N supervised research. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.